

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: Sabri Ülker Foundation

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"Let's meet!" Event Validation Report - TURKEY

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of Sabri Ülker Foundation for the organisation and validation of the **Culinary Event in İstanbul, Turkey on January 24th, 2023**. This event is one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the the Let’s Meet Culinary Event in İstanbul, Turkey.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
Welcome	Before the event started, the agroBRIDGES project was explained to all participants. The aims and objectives of the project and what has been done so far are summarized. It was explained that the event was within the scope of the project and the expected outputs from this event were discussed.	12:00 – 12:15	Nişantaşı University - Department of Gastronomy
Menu design	Participants designed a menu of local products to promote local products that will contribute to the short food supply chain. For the menu design, the lecturers in the Gastronomy Department guided the participants and talked about local products. A menu using local products was designed.	12.15-12.45	Nişantaşı University - Department of Gastronomy
Cooking	The chefs were divided into 4 groups and the recipes for the menus were distributed. Then, the gastronomic kitchen was used to prepare the meals within the given time.	13.00-14.30	Nişantaşı University - Department of Gastronomy – Cooking Lab
Tasting and discussion	The menus and delicacies prepared in the gastronomic kitchen were tasted. In the meantime, the necessity of	14.30-15.00	Nişantaşı University - Department of Gastronomy – Cooking Lab Discussion Area

	<p>raising awareness in the field of gastronomy in order to strengthen the SFSC was also mentioned. This part was the most enjoyable part of the event for everyone. Because the chefs made dishes that they had not cooked before and their tastes were amazing. They also discovered that they could bring the taste to the fore by using local products!</p>		
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2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

The event was planned in cooperation with Nişantaşı University. The event, which was held at the Sariyer Campus of the University in Istanbul, was hosted by the Gastronomy department. Meals at the event were prepared in the kitchens of the Gastronomy Department, with the comments of the people attending the event, and by the chefs invited to the event in the open kitchen area (where the audience sees all stages of the food being prepared behind the glass). The following photo shows the area where the event was held and one of the dishes (dessert) below.

Figure 1: The chefs and organizing team

Figure 2: Planning with the chefs before the event starts

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

The Communication Director, a Project Manager and the Nutrition Executive from the Sabri Ülker Foundation attended the event. As a guide for creating a menu with local products at the event, lecturer Assistant Professor **Dr. Gamze Şanlı Ak** took part in the event as a nutritionist. In addition, Nişantaşı University Gastronomy Department Head **Dr. Ahmet Süreyya Koçtürk** (Chef) also participated in the event and supported the menu planning.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Lecturer	1	Development of promo material	External	0.5 days
Chef	1	Food and drinks for guests	External	0.5 days
Project manager	1	Involving the chef and lecturer in the process, providing participants	In-house	2 days

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

Sabri Ülker Foundation held a preliminary meeting with Nişantaşı University - Gastronomy Department summarizing the agroBRIDGES project and its aims. In this direction, it was decided to plan an event with dishes cooked with local products to increase the use of local products by the cooks. The date of the event was planned by making the relevant meetings 1 month before the event. Then the event was completed on January 24.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The invitation of the participants was made with the announcement post on the big screen of the University at the school entrance. The event has been planned as an event open to all cooks on campus on the day of the event. Apart from this, an announcement image was prepared to be sent to the gastronomy WhatsApp groups for the participation of outside participants and was sent to the department teachers.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

After explaining the project and the event to the chefs, the event started with the distribution of the determined recipes to the chefs. All the meals to be prepared on the day of the event consisting of recipes developed by the academics at Nişantaşı University with local products. The reason for this is the dissemination of the use of local products, which is the most important goal of the agroBRIDGES project. For this reason, awareness was created in chefs by drawing attention to local products. You can see all the recipes made with local products in the image below.

The designed menu consists of dishes using local products from Turkey. Before the event, the lecturers of the gastronomy department conducted a preliminary study on how to design a menu by researching local products that are not frequently used in Turkey. On the day of the event, the menu took its final form with the contributions of the chefs. The menu included sea bass with peanut sauce, date balls, and village chicken with bechamel. All dishes were made with local spices, which are not used frequently but are very common in Turkey. Seabass and chicken were procured from local producers.

Figure 4: Meals with local products

Figure 5: Sample recipe

3.2 Event participation

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Consumers	53
Total	53

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Question	Answers				
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	Yes	No	Not Sure		
Attendee answers	53	0	0		
Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	Very informative	Relatively Informative	Neutral	Not Informative	Not Informative at all
Attendee answers	41	11	1	0	0
Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local food businesses, restaurants, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all
Attendee answers	26	21	6	0	0
Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very Helpful	Not Helpful at all
Attendee answers	23	27	3	0	0
Did you find enough information about how and where to find the local restaurants and kitchens and other hospitality businesses you've met?	Enough and very precise information	Enough information, but I would need more details	Enough information but I need to search	Not enough information	No information at all

			further on my own			
Attendee answers	38	15	0	0	0	
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Attendee answers	33	14	5	1	0	0

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

We think a similar culinary event would be nice in relation to local agriculture. Unfortunately, such activities are not common in the existing ecosystem. This event will therefore set an example. The concept of the event resulted in high satisfaction, as can be seen from the survey results applied to the participants.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes, because all the participants left very satisfied. Also, all the cooks who attended this event now understood how important it is to develop recipes with local products. To increase the consumption of local products, similar events can be made more in the field of gastronomy.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

Yes, it was very instructive and much appreciated. Guidelines and templates could not be used for this event because the announcement of the event was published by Nişantaşı University, and they stated that they could not use existing designs due to their internal procedures (digital screen resizing required resizing the design templates).

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

Yes, we had no problems for guidelines.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, it was in a format adaptable to the entire ecosystem.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

More than 50 individuals were targeted to participate in the event. Although this goal was achieved at the end of the event and the event was completed with over 50 participants, SUF aimed to hold this event in a larger kitchen with over 150 participants. However, since there is not enough equipment and more than 50 participants cannot be accepted in the Gastronomy Kitchen at the same time (due to hygiene and kitchen rules), the number of participants has not been as much as SUF's target.

4.1.4 Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

To reach more participants for a similar event, local agricultural producers can be added to the University collaboration and a culinary event can be organized that brings producers and consumers closer by completing the event with a roundtable discussion.